

COST RETURNS OF ON CLUPEIIDS FISHERY RESOURCES IN RIVER STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The increased demand for fish in Nigeria compelled the artisanal fishery sector to aggressively seek for fishing inputs that will enhance their output. The study aimed at evaluating the economic viability of the Ghana boat in artisanal fishery of the Rivers state, Nigeria. Primary data was obtained from a five-stage purposive sampling procedure, various fishing communities' showed preferences for alternative Craft, with reference to its adoptability to enhance high yield. Ghana boat in the study areas significantly increased fish production ($P>0.05$). Whereas the popular motorized and non-motorized smaller Crafts, gradually being substituted by Ghana boat. Application of Marginal Costing technique examined the cost and earnings of Ghana boat in some fishing communities in Rivers State of the Niger Delta. The result indicated that to own a Ghana boat requires, an initial investment of =N=2,100.00 (craft and gear), operational cost of =N=60,000 and yielded margin of =N=40,000 per trip from an average sales. Returns are especially sensitive to changes in market values, fuel/lubricants and natural constraints. The results of cost-profit analysis depend on opportunity to fishers by adopting the optimum strategy, earnings; per fishing trip are shared depending on the individual arrangement among fisher folks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

KEYWORDS;Cost, Returns, Half-Dugout, River State

INTRODUCTION

The consumption of fish and seafood products remained an important component of the diet of people living in the Niger Delta and Nigeria at large. Many Coastal Communities in Nigeria are dependent on marine resources from near shore and off shore environment as a primary source of protein and income. This is also common of many fishing communities (Munro 1996), with the loss of their resources substantially importing food security and socioeconomic structure (Sadovy 2002). FAO (1999) reported that the amount of food fish consumption has risen in sub-Saharan African, mainly because of the rapid growth in these regions. The aggregate trend of demand pull suggests that the fisheries sector needs urgent attention in reducing or eliminating disequilibria of the product by injecting new techniques. Thus, FAO (2000a), opined that as a result of sustained, increasing fishing pressure, most stocks in the wild today are classified as fully exploited, in decline or in recovery. Dadan (2005) estimated Nigeria fish requirement deficit at 1.5 million metric tons, while Ajayi (2002), inferred a deficit met by importation at a great cost in foreign exchange to the country.

Preliminary analyses suggest that immigrant Ghanaia fishermen dominated the clupeid fisheries for bonga, *Ethmologa fimbriata*, sardine, *Sardinella maderensis*, and shad, *Elisha africana*. Fishing activities on the Bonny Island and Rivers State in general can be described as Artisanal fisheries dominance. The economic characteristic of traditional crafts may be described as low cost, low yield, low earnings, low savings and probably low technology. Half-Dugout Canoe "Ghana boats", however, is becoming popular among artisanal fishermen on the Bonny Island and other fishing communities in Rivers State. It has the capacity to fish offshore beyond the 5 nautical miles. The craft (Ghana boat) efficiently exploits fish resources,

reducing hour's trawls and absorbing more labour, hence, enhancing income generation around coastal areas of Rivers States, Nigeria.

The study showed that the improved craft in the study areas has impacted positively upon the product fish. The socio-economic environment of the fishermen is of immense importance as it has direct bearings on the productivity. The fishing industry is a long standing profession and most of the times the crafts is location specific. The report evaluates findings on the economic impact of Ghana boat and income generations in some fishing communities of four River systems in River State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Eight fishing communities were randomly selected two villages each from Bonny River system, Sombreiro River system, New Calabar River system and Andoni River system all in Rivers state, Nigeria. Five research surveys were carried out in each of the eight fishing communities selected from October, 2004 to July, 2005. Based on the objective of study, a convenience sampling procedures were adopted in selecting four local fishermen from each community, trained to be collecting data on daily fishing activities. Quantitative information gathering technique of Focal Group Discussion (FGD) (Horemans, 1998) was employed for structured questionnaire administration, while ocular and physical inspection coupled with Semi Structure Interviews (SSI) were the methods used to obtain information on landing, fishermen personal data, income generations, fisheries activities, craft, gear, out boat engine (OBE) target fishery and the catch.

Model specification: Two variables for evaluation exist in this model; fish production (artisanal catches) and Ghana boat. The fish production is the dependent variable, while Out Boat Engine (OBE) Ghana boat is the independent variable. The data collected from the study was thereafter subjected to Institute of Cost and Management Accountants (ICMA) England's Marginal Costs Analysis as used by (Habib 2004). This is to determine the economic profits accruable to artisanal fishermen in the study areas. Thus, the model is;

$$S = Vc + Fc \pm /L \text{ or } S - Vc = Fc \pm /L.$$

Where;

S = sales

Vc = variable cost

Fc = fixed cost

= profit

L = loss

A case in point, landing, is quantity of fish stock a fisherman is able to catch and make it available for demand in a particular time /season at a receiving point. Total Revenue (TR) is the total amount made from sale of catch. Total Variable cost (TVC) is the total cost incurred during fishing trip. Total Gross Margin (TGM) is the gross profit that is obtainable from fishing activities. Therefore, cost and return was used to evaluate the margin value of Ghana boat from artisanal fishing. The fixed expenses depreciated in value at a 5%, 50%, 25%, craft, gear/spare parts and OBE engine respectively, per annul was tested during the surveys (2004-2005), (to further prove its economic viability). One basic assumption made in this study is that 45 weeks represent a year other things been equal, while a normal fishing trip in the study areas last 4 days.

A typical Nigerian made Half-Dugout Ghana Boat in displayed after a fishing trip.

Fig. 1, A typical half dugout Ghana boat. Source: Field Survey 2004-2005.

RESULTS

Two hundred and nine (209) questionnaires were administered during the survey period, out of which detailed information concerning the cost and returns of Ghana boats was provided in different fishing communities in River state Nigeria. The two guides to the research team also provided further information on their 14.4m long dugout Ghana boat with 40HP OBE, bait, 200pcs stainless ring hook and line sinkers and floaters (Bonny Island).

Cost Analysis

Table 1: Presents an average sale, fixed and variable cost incurred from a fishing trip:

Details	=N=
a. Sales/trip	100,000

Table 1; Investment cost. Sources: Field survey 2004/2005

Fixed expenses	=N=
14.4mt.Ghana boat (Dugout)	1,000,000
Painting/Transport to Nigeria	500,000
40Hp Yamaha Engine	400,000
600mts.of long line	15,000
Stainless Ring Hook (200pcs)	100,000
Security Lights (6pcs)	62,500
Miscellaneous	22,500
Sub-Total	2,100,000
Variable Cost (on every trip 4 days)	
Fueling/Lubrication	44,000
Ice block	6,000
Feeding	8,000
Precautionary	2,000
Sub-Total	60,000
Grand Total	2,160,000

Marginal cost Equation

For the sake of convenience, the elements of costs can be written in the form of an equation as follows;

$$\text{Variable cost} + \text{fixed expenses} \pm \text{Profit/loss}$$

Or Sales = Variable cost + fixed expenses ± Profit/loss

Hence, margin per trip (4days) is;

	=N=
Sales	100,000.00
Variable cost	60,000.00
Contribution	40,000.00

The annual contribution for a year will then be a unit contribution/trip × total landings, hence, 40,000 × 79 landings =N=3,160,000. While the expected annual profit (), will be TR-TC. Therefore; TR=unit sales × landings/year

$$=100,000 \times 79= 7,900,000 \text{ (annual sales).}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TC} &= \text{FC} + \text{VC} \\ \text{TC} &= 2,100,000 + 4,740,000 = 6,840,000. \\ \text{Annual Profit; annual sales- total cost} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{S} - \text{TC} \\ &7,900,000 - 6,840,000 = 1,060,000. \end{aligned}$$

Break Even Point/Landing
(in landings)

Fixed cost	2,100,000.00
Variable cost/trip	60,000.00
Selling/trip	100,000.00

At BEP therefore, $\frac{\text{fixed cost}}{\text{selling price/trip} - \text{variable cost/trip}}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Substituting the value, such as,} \\ &= \frac{2100000}{100000 - 60000} = \frac{2100000}{40000} \\ &= 52.5 \text{ landings} \end{aligned}$$

Break Even Point = Units of landing x Selling price/trip
(In terms of sales) = 52.2 x 100000 = =N= 5,250,000.

Depreciation

A straight line method is used in the depreciation calculation; the result is as follows;

Ghana Boat	5%
Fishing Gear & spare parts	50%
40Hp Yamaha Engine	25%

The total cumulative cost of depreciation for the 1st phase is estimated at =N=235,500.00. Having estimated the cost of depreciation, the remaining value of capital items was estimated as follows;

	=N=		=N=
Ghana Boat	1,500,000	@ 5%	75,000
Fishing Gear & spare parts	115,000	@ 50%	57,500
40Hp Yamaha Engine	400,000	@ 25%	100,000
Total	2,015,000		232,500

Break Even Point

The introduction of depreciation and interest will change our BEP to;

	=N=
Total investment	2,160,000.00
Interest@10%	216,000.00
Depreciation	232,500.00
Total cost	2,608,500.00
Annual sales (100,000 × 79 trip)	= 7,900,000.00

Since, $\text{TR} - \text{TC}$, then, $7,900,000 - 2,608,500 = 5,291,500$.

Sensitivity analysis

	=N=
Sales	100,000.00
Variable cost	69,000.00
Margin	31,000.00

Break even point/landing

	=N=
Sales	100,000.00
Fixed cost	2,310,000.00
Variable cost	69,000.00
Total cost	= 2,379,000

Annual sales (100,000 × 79 trip) = 7,900,000.00

Since, $\text{TR} - \text{TC}$, then, $7,900,000 - 2,379,000 = 5,521,000$.

At Break Even Point therefore, $\frac{2,310,000}{100,000} = 23.1$ Landings
 $= 100,000 \times 23.1 = 2,310,000$.

	=N=
Total investment	2,376,000.00
Interest@10%	356,400.00
Depreciation	348,750.00
Total cost	3,081,150.00

Annual profit (100,000 × 79 trip) = 7,900,000.00

Since, $\text{TR} - \text{TC}$ then, $7,900,000 - 3,081,150 = 4,818,850$.

The average annual profit made from sales of 79 trips, depreciation =N=348,750 and at 10% interest was =N=5,521,000.

DISCUSSION

The results from the survey data shows a positive relationship exist between Ghana boat and increased artisanal fishery in Rivers State area of the Niger Delta, Nigeria. The study indicated a high profit margin and providing cost-effective to the new craft. This means an increase in labour (employment opportunities)

which will eventually increase the output. However, this may not be unconnected to the excessive exploitation of the resources (fish).

Based on the sensitivity test, the following assumptions were made:

1. that the total investment cost was 10% and sales revenue constant
2. that interest rate increased to 15%
3. that both total investment cost and interest rate increased which also raised total average depreciation pegged at 50%.

Generally, not all components would have increased by the same percent. However, at these conservative estimates, Ghana boat exhibited high profit potentials as explained under various assumptions, the following can be inferred:-

- The variable cost is increased that would reduce the profit margin of participants.
- Under ceteris paribus the investment will be able to payback in possible short period of time.

In this context, investment on Ghana boat would facilitate unhindered flow and increased level of fish production and animal protein intake in Nigeria. It will increase the income generation capacity of the fishery workers and reduce the level of poverty among participants.

Prospects

One of the unfortunate outcomes of the non-powered small traditional craft remained unchanged (low yield, labour intensive etc.) through the years. Their contribution towards marine and the sea fisheries is small. Thus, plays a major role to the welfare of fishing community, and remained the most popular at different landing centers. In any case, at present the impact of mechanization has been so great on small-scale fisheries, that a number of non-powered are now getting fitted with engines.

The introduction of Ghana boat along the coast of River State not only has it gain momentum but it seems as crucial towards economic transformation. The availability and abundance of created inherited fishing skill throughout the entire coastline, and the interaction with nature, fishing folk has changed or at least increased domestic production nearly large enough to supply the fish/food for a rapidly growing population in Nigeria. The survey of 12-04-2005 in Oke-Eri one of the fishing communities in Andoni Local Government Area, a 14.5 meters long plank built Ghana boat using Monofilaments net, operated by nine crew members landed 784 kg of different species at peak season. Notable impressive results were also recorded in other fishing communities from increased application of Ghana boat among artisanal fishing sector.

It is interesting to note that the craft in our waters stimulate wealth and distribution among users. It must be emphasized that the boat itself does not necessarily improve the distribution of income. However, it is logical to believe that when economic activities are taking place, it can to some extent change the pattern of income distribution, at least to greater equity without having to make anyone worse off in absolute terms. The craft, also gives impetus to industrial progress by absorbing the ever-growing surplus of labour, combat poverty, by providing capital formation base and other social plight. The size and weight of Ghana boat implies efficiency and fuller utilization of resources than the popular smaller boat.

RECOMMENDATION

The economic structure of Nigeria at take-off stage was described as agriculturally base and labour intensive which is strongly related to technological advancement and productivity growth. There potentials are still waiting to be developed. A holistic approach to the artisanal fisheries may positively transform Nigerian's fish demand deficit or at least reduce it and contribute towards economic development from the availability of abundance resources.

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